

Ultrasonic velocity studies of dimethyl phosphoryl acetyl phosphate in ethanol-water system at 30°

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Ultrasonic velocities of various concentrations of dimethyl phosphoryl acetyl phosphate in aqueous ethanol mixtures have been measured at 30° by using single crystal interferometer at a frequency of 3 MHz. By using velocity, density, viscosity and concentration data, various acoustical parameters are calculated and the results are interpreted in terms of solvent-solute and solute-solute interactions. The positive values of solvation number implies the structure-forming tendency.

Dimethyl phosphoryl acetyl phosphate is a well-known pesticide. Depending upon its physicochemical properties, its use under the given conditions can be selected. The physical and chemical properties are strongly dependent on the structure of the pesticides. Further, knowledge of acoustical properties of any solution provides information about the interaction occurring in the solution¹. In continuation with our previous work^{2,3}, the present work describes the ultrasonic velocity studies of dimethyl phosphoryl acetyl phosphate in pure water and varying proportions of ethanol (10, 30 and 50%) at 30°.

Results and Discussion

Various acoustical parameters, like adiabatic compressibility (β), acoustic impedance (Z), intermolecular free length (L_f), Rao's molar sound function (R), relaxation strength (r), van der Waals constant (b), internal pressure (π), relative association (R_A) and solvation number (S_n) were calculated using velocity (U), density (ρ) and viscosity (η) data with the help of standard equations presented in our earlier publications².

Tables 1 and 2 show the variation of these parameters with concentrations (C) in all the ethanol-water systems. It is observed that velocity increases nonlinearly in 10% similar to that in pure water. Increase in U indicates association among molecules. There is possibility of H-bond formation between oxygen of solvent and solute molecules. The H-bond formation strengthens the intermolecular forces resulting in a decrease of compressibility and increase of U and Z . Further, it suggests a structure-promoting tendency of added electrolyte in 10% ethanol and pure water. But in 30% ethanol system, velocity is found to be almost constant except at 1 M where slight decrease is observed. However, in 50% ethanol system, slight decrease in U is observed after 0.6 M. This indicates that the reverse pheno-

Table 1. Variation of ρ , U , Z , β , b and R with concentration at 30°

Concn. M	ρ $g\ cm^{-3}$	$10^5 U$ $cm\ s^{-1}$	$10^5 Z$ $g\ cm^{-2}$	$10^{11} \beta$ $cm^2\ dyn^{-1}$	b cm^3	R
Water						
0.00	1.0000	1.5130	1.5130	4.3683	16.305	959.15
0.20	1.0046	1.5220	1.5290	4.2971	20.922	1223.2
0.40	1.0136	1.5340	1.5549	4.1925	25.336	1475.8
0.60	1.0281	1.5386	1.5726	4.1330	29.636	1719.5
0.80	1.0313	1.5452	1.5935	4.0612	33.762	1953.7
1.00	1.0402	1.5578	1.6204	3.9616	37.784	2184.2
10% Ethanol						
0.00	0.9843	1.5706	1.5460	4.1185	19.274	1140.1
0.20	0.9928	1.5757	1.5646	4.0558	23.846	1402.6
0.40	1.0013	1.5800	1.5821	4.0006	28.284	1656.3
0.60	1.0102	1.5756	1.5917	3.9875	32.560	1897.3
0.80	1.0182	1.5818	1.6106	3.9252	36.758	2136.8
1.00	1.0296	1.5960	1.6432	3.8130	40.636	2361.2
30% Ethanol						
0.00	0.9510	1.6025	1.5252	4.0914	25.513	1506.6
0.20	0.9646	1.6008	1.5441	4.0456	30.027	1763.7
0.40	0.9739	1.5995	1.5578	4.0133	34.471	2016.0
0.60	0.9829	1.6008	1.5734	3.9703	38.778	2260.6
0.80	0.9929	1.6001	1.5887	3.9338	42.866	2491.5
1.00	1.0032	1.5992	1.6033	3.9026	46.773	2710.8
50% Ethanol						
0.00	0.9116	1.4712	1.3411	5.0682	32.309	1853.1
0.20	0.9265	1.4864	1.3771	4.8854	36.866	2111.6
0.40	0.9364	1.4903	1.3955	4.8084	41.395	2364.4
0.60	0.9475	1.4910	1.4127	4.7477	45.659	2600.6
0.80	0.9569	1.4880	1.4239	4.7197	49.841	2829.9
1.00	0.9651	1.4860	1.4341	4.7210	53.949	3052.5

menon takes place with increasing concentration of pesticide in 50% ethanol-water system. Thus, in 50% ethanol, interaction between ethanol and water becomes more important which plays important role in the change in the

Table 2. Variation of L_f , W , η , π and S_n with concentration at 30°

Concn. <i>M</i>	L_f Å	W	$10^3\eta$ poise	π atoms	S_n
Water					
0.00	0.4020	543.535	7.973	2596.714	–
0.20	0.3987	693.471	8.222	1979.591	19.8
0.40	0.3938	837.408	8.833	1639.525	19.5
0.60	0.3910	976.738	9.653	1427.570	19.0
0.80	0.3876	1110.915	10.104	1252.247	19.9
1.00	0.3828	1243.032	11.331	1158.242	19.3
10% Ethanol					
0.00	0.3903	643.494	10.682	2465.917	–
0.20	0.3873	792.522	11.304	1982.622	18.6
0.40	0.3847	936.887	11.852	1664.593	20.3
0.60	0.3840	1074.699	12.963	1479.680	28.1
0.80	0.3810	1211.457	13.779	1322.185	26.2
1.00	0.3755	1340.234	14.865	1214.317	21.2
30% Ethanol					
0.00	0.3890	845.427	16.752	2263.666	–
0.20	0.3868	991.658	17.732	1925.132	20.5
0.40	0.3853	1135.152	18.111	1656.773	24.7
0.60	0.3832	1274.457	15.5094	1334.960	24.6
0.80	0.3814	1406.698	19.830	1341.084	25.9
1.00	0.3799	1532.890	18.918	1181.107	27.7
50% Ethanol					
0.00	0.4330	1037.720	20.326	2020.234	–
0.20	0.4251	1184.603	22.581	1811.682	5.5
0.40	0.4217	1328.307	22.378	1571.745	7.9
0.60	0.4190	1463.409	33.993	1723.237	9.9
0.80	0.4178	1594.864	25.044	1334.032	12.5
1.00	0.4166	1724.234	25.044	1214.734	14.9

behaviour of solution. Due to insolubility of solute at higher percentage of ethanol and pure ethanol, further study was not possible.

Decrease of β with increasing concentration of solute might be due to aggregation of solvent molecules around solute molecules indicating strong solvent-solute interac-

tions. The values of R , W and b increased linearly with concentration in all the solvent systems studied, indicating solute-solvent interactions. Internal pressure decreases with increase in concentration indicating thereby decrease of cohesive forces.

The solvation number (S_n) is useful in understanding the structure-making and structure-breaking tendency of added electrolyte in a solvent. Table 2 shows positive values of S_n in all the concentrations for all the compositions of ethanol-water mixtures, indicating thereby the structure-forming tendency of pesticide in all the solvent compositions. The increase in S_n indicates the decrease of ion-ion interaction and hence occurrence of the association with solvent molecules. However, in pure water, almost constant S_n values over the whole range of concentration indicate that ion-ion interaction or association of pesticide with solvent molecules is not changed with concentration. In case of 50% ethanol, solvation is minimum because of greater interaction between water and ethanol. Thus, due to dissociation, solvation number is low in comparison to other systems.

Experimental

Distilled ethanol and double-distilled water were used. For water and ethanol-water compositions, solutions of different concentrations of the pesticide were prepared. Density, sound velocity and viscosity were measured according to our previous publication².

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